

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

COLLEGE OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES

PROCEEDINGS OF THE MEETING OF BOARD OF STUDIES HELD ON 20.10.2021 AT 9:30 AM IN THE BOARD ROOM

Members present:

1. Prof. Devaseelan S	Chairman,
2. Mr. Naveen Bappanadu	Member
3. Mrs. Swathi D	Member
4. Ms. Varsha A C	Member
5. Ms. Kavya Shettigar K	Member
6. Mrs. Swathi Krishnan	Member
7. Ms. Brilly Anto	Member
8. Mrs. Priyadhersini. S	Member
9. Ms. Maureen Edwards	Member
10. Dr. Vrinda J Bhat	External Member
11. Dr. David Rosario	External Member
12. B Balaji Narayan	Industrial Expert

The BOS discussed the following agenda:

1. Approve the minutes of the last Meeting of the BOS held on 10.06.2020.
2. NEP 2021 based Syllabus implement.
3. Update on Credit Based System
4. Proposed a course name change of Digital and Cyber Forensics to 'Digital Forensics and Cyber Security'
5. Proposed M.Sc. Cyber Forensics Specialization (a. Malware Forensics b. Ethical hacking in Network Security) and Eligibility Criteria to be initiated.
6. Update on syllabus of M.Sc. Courses
7. Commencement of Offline Classes

Agenda No. 1: Confirmations of the minutes of Last Meeting of Board of Studies which was held on 12.06.2020. The Resolution was taken as per the suggestions of the BOS Members in the last meeting, all the Allied Health Sciences Courses were asked to update the changes proposed by the BOS Members.

Agenda No. 2: The Chairman proposed that the syllabus to be updated as per NEP 2021. The College of Allied Health Sciences all courses were to be updated as per the regulations laid down in National Education Policy 2021. The suggestion was approved by the BOS and all the courses were asked to update the syllabus as proposed by the Chairman.

Agenda No. 3: As it was suggested that the syllabus based on the NEP 2021 to be implemented, the credit allocation for the subjects must be changed accordingly. It was suggested to follow the new choice-based credit system for every course to be followed and resolution was taken accordingly, updates and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 4: It was proposed by Ms. Varsha A C to change the course name of “Digital and Cyber Forensics” to “Digital Forensics and Cyber Security.” Resolution was taken accordingly, and changes were approved as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 5: It was suggested by the BOS Member to add two specializations for M.Sc. Cyber Forensics as Malware Forensics and Ethical hacking in Network Security. It was also suggested for initiating the Eligibility Criteria for those students who prefer the Course. Changes were approved and Resolution was taken accordingly as proposed by the BOS.

Agenda No. 6: The suggestion was given to update the syllabus of all the M.Sc. Courses as per current syllabus criteria. The resolution was taken accordingly as proposed by the BOS, it was decided to update the syllabus by considering the suggestions of external members and stake holders.

Agenda No. 7: The Chairperson stated the need to begin with offline classes and to keep curriculum coverage as most preferred task. The decision was taken to commence with the offline classes. Resolution was taken accordingly as per the suggestion proposed by the Chairperson and was approved by the BOS as suggested.

The meeting was concluded at 11:30 AM with a vote of thanks by Ms. Kavya Shettigar K, Member of Board of Studies.

Prof. Devaseelan S,
Chairman,
BOS in Allied Health Science

Members present:

Prof. Devaseelan S

Mr. Naveen Bappanadu

Mrs. Swathi D

Ms. Varsha A C

Ms. Kavya Shettigar K

Mrs. Swathi Krishnan

Ms. Brilly Anto

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